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Report on FRACTESUS communication activities

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¹ **Nature:** **R** -Document, report; **DEM** -Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC** -Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**; **ETHICS** -Ethics requirement; **ORDP** -Open Research Data Pilot; **DATA** -data sets, microdata, etc.

² **Dissemination level:** **PU** -Public; **CO** -Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

D.6.2 – Report on FRACTESUS communication activities

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1 Introduction

Since the beginning of the project, profiles were established on the main social/professional networks (see D6.1): ResearchGate, Twitter, LinkedIn, and Facebook. Unfortunately, in March 2023, ResearchGate decided to discontinue its project section. Therefore, the FRACTESUS profile is no longer available on this platform. Despite this drawback, the project garnered significant traffic across the rest of platforms, which are more than those initially foreseen in the project proposal (only ResearchGate and Twitter), demonstrating the public interest in FRACTESUS’ online presence. Below, the key metrics reached with the project social network by the end of the project are presented.

2 Communication on social networks

The FRACTESUS X (Twitter) profile was launched in October 2020 (<https://twitter.com/fractesus>), serving as useful platform to disseminate project outcomes to the general public and media. Consistent updates, including tweets and retweets, were provided regularly. Besides, links to EU organisations and H2020 projects were established. Impressively, the platform has obtained 8657 impressions, attracted 5619 profile visits, and garnered 27 followers through 68 tweets. The X profile page is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. FRACTESUS profile in X.

The FRACTESUS **LinkedIn** page, established in October 2020 (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/fractesus-h2020/>), aims to connect the project with a broader professional sector, beyond the scientific field. The project profile has obtained 22847 impressions, garnered 98 followers, attracted 985 visits through 57 posts. The LinkedIn project profile page is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. FRACTESUS profile in LinkedIn.

The FRACTESUS **Facebook** profile was created in October 2020 (<https://www.facebook.com/Fractesus-H2020-100313765184397/>), providing another common social network to engage with the general public. During this time, the profile garnered 2197 reaches, shared 38 publications, attracted 168 visits and got 13 followers. The Facebook profile page is shown in Figure 3.

Furthermore, the FRACTESUS **website** was launched by the project coordinator, SCK-CEN, in October 2020 (<https://fractesus-h2020.eu/>). This website, developed with the specifications outlined in D7.1, the project management platform, serves as an online resource accessible to the general public and to the proper consortium members. The website, besides the homepage, includes the following sections: Objectives, Mission Statement, Methodology, Cooperation, About Us, Public Documents and contacts. Significant traffic has been observed all throughout the project. Figure 4 shows the homepage of the FRACTESUS website.

Figure 3. FRACTESUS profile on Facebook.

Figure 4. FRACTESUS website.

3 Conclusions

Figure 4 shows a summary of the key metrics (impressions + visits) obtained in the different project communication networks. It is clear the better performance was obtained with LinkedIn platform, closely followed by X, and with Facebook being the social network with the lowest level of interactions by.

Figure 5. Summary of FRACTESUS profiles impressions/visits.

This being said, all these communication tools allowed the project to achieve a high level of interaction with both the scientific community and the general public. The expectations of the project proposal have been achieved, and the experience gained in FRACTESUS will be highly valuable in future initiatives.